

ISSN (E): 2181-4570

**PATISSON (Cucurbita pepo var. melopepo) O'SIMLIGINI EKISH
TEXNOLOGIYASI VA PARVARISHLASH USULLARI**

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Annotatsiya.

Qovoqdoshlar oilasi vakillarini poya tuzilishi bo'yicha 2 guruhga (tup hosil qiluvchi va palak otib o'suvchi guruhlarga) ajratish mumkin. Biz o'stirayotgan patisson o'simligi tup hosil qiluvchi guruhga kiradi. Patisson – qovoqdoshlar oilasiga mansub bir yillik o'simlikdir. Meva eti sersuv. Patisson palagi tik o'suvchi, butasimon sershox o'simlik hisoblanadi. Ildizi yaxshi rivojlangan. Poyasi va barg bandlari nisbatan yo'g'on. Barglari o'rtacha kattalikda, dag'al, 3 yoki 5 qirrali. Gullari yirik, rangi sariq rangda bo'lib, poyalarda yakka-yakka joylashadi. Mevasi — qovoqcha, mayda, shakli yulduzsimon va boshqa shakllarda bo'ladi. Yangi tukkan mevalari rangi och yashil, meva katta bo'lgan sari rangi oqarib, ayrim mevalar yuzasida och yashil dog'lar yoki tasmalar paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Ularning 6-8 kunlik mevasi iste'mol qilinadi.

Abstract.

Representatives of the pumpkin family can be divided into 2 groups based on the structure of the stem (stem-forming and shoot-growing groups). The patisson plant that we are growing belongs to the bush-forming group. Patisson is an annual plant belonging to the pumpkin family. The flesh of the fruit is watery. Patisson palagi is an upright, shrub-like branched plant. The root is well developed. Stem and leaf bands are relatively thick. The leaves are medium-sized, coarse, 3- or 5-sided. The flowers are large, yellow in color and placed singly on the stems. The fruit is a pumpkin, small, star-shaped and other shapes. . The color of freshly harvested fruits is light green, as the fruit grows, the color becomes pale, and light green spots or bands may appear on the surface of some fruits. Their fruits are eaten after 6-8 days.

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Kalit so'zlar: patisson, ekish sxemasi, agrotexnikasi, tavsiya etiladigan navlar, ekish metodikasi.

Key words: pumpkin, planting scheme, agrotechnics, recommended varieties, planting methods.

Patisson mayda mevali sershox o'simlik hisoblanadi. Patisson o'simligi juda issiq talab o'simlikdir. Uni aprel oyida qator va tup oralig'i 70×70 yoki 80×80 sm sxemada ekish mumkin. O'suv davrida qator oralari yumshatilib, oziqlantiriladi va sug'oriladi. Patisson suvga ham juda talabchandır.

Mevasi tarkibida 6,0—6,5% quruq modda, 2,5-2,9% qand va vitaminlar mavjud. Urug'ida moy va santanin bor. Hosildorligi 150-200 s/rani tashkil etadi.

Patissonni parvarishlash: patisson uchun eng yaxshi o'tmishdosh ekinlar bu g'alla, karam, sabzi, makkajo'xori va sholi hisoblanadi.

Ekish muddati: Janubiy viloyatlarda 1-20 aprelda, markaziy viloyatlarda 20-30 aprelda, shimoliy viloyatlarda 1-15-maygacha ekish mumkin.

1-rasm. Patisson guli.

Ekish sxemasi: $(110 + 70)/2 \times 50-60$ sm. Urug' sarfi- 3-4 kg/ga.

O'g'itlash: Go'ngni 20-30 t/ga ishlatish mumkin. Azot esa 200 kg/ga, fosforni 150 kg/ga, kaliyni 50 kg/ga ishlatiladi.

Sug'orish: O'suv davrida 12-16 marta sug'oriladi. Sug'orish me'yori 500-600 m³/ga. Hozirgi kunda O'zbekistonda patissonning 2 navi yetishtiriladi.

Zarkokil. Ertapishar nav, o'suv davri- 50-60 kun. Palagi kichik, deyarli kalta. Bargi yuraksimon, qirrali, yashil rangli. Mevasi yapaloq yulduzsimon, ko'p bo'lakchalar tarelkasifat birlashgan, mayda, yashil rangli, biologik yetilganda sariq, vazni 25-30 g.

Hosildorligi: 6-7 t/ga. Oziq-ovqat, konserva va chorvachilikda foydalaniladi.

Mamlakatimiz hududida barcha viloyatlarda ekish uchun tavsiya qilingan.

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2-rasm. Patissonning 2-3 kunlik mevasi.

Oq-13. O'rta pishar nav. Tup hosil qilib o'sadi. Unib chiqqandan to meva tukkuncha bo'lgan davr 55-67 kunning tashkil etadi. Mevasi disksimon. Chetlari sezilar sezilmas bo'laklarga bo'lingan. Bu 2 nav davlat reestriga kiritilgan.

3-rasm. Tadqiqot maydonchasi.

Patissonning serhosil, kasalliklarga chidamli duragaylarini ko'paytirish maqsadida turli xil navlarini ekib o'rganishni maqsad qildik. Tadqiqotimizda quyidagi navlari ekib o'rganilyapti. Bulardan: patisson sun, patisson disk, solnishko, patisson groshik, patisson arbuzinka, patisson sinishka, zontik, mini kroschka, karapuz, pyatichok, polo F1, NLO beliy, klyaksa, cheburashka, marsianin va h.k.lar.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

1. B.Zuyev., A. Abdullayev. Sabzavot ekinlari va ularni yetishtirish texnologiyasi. O'zbekiston nashriyoti.157-166 betlar.
2. S. Isaev, S. Khasanov, Y. Ashirov, T. Karabaeva, A. Gofirov, In E3S Web of Conferences,244,02012(2021)

3. T. Ostonakulov, V. Zuyev, A. Kadirkhujayev, "Navruz" press, 1, 452 (2018)
4. Briefing, V. Zuyev, A. Dirie, M. Mukhamedov, National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 478 (Sharq Press, Tashkent, 2002)
5. N. Teshayev, B. Mamadaliyev, A. Ibragimov, S. Khasanov, Inter Carto. Inter GIS, 26 (3), 324-333 (2020)
6. E. Domblides, N. Shmykova, G. Khimich, I. Korotseva, L. Kan, A. Domblides, A. Soldatenko, In VI International Symposium on Cucurbits, 42-48 (2019)
7. A. Shantasov, S. Sokolov, A. Bocharnikov, V. Maletina, Vegetable crops of Russia, 3, 11 (2015).
8. S. Isaev, S. Khasanov, Y. Ashirov, A. Gofirov, T. Karabaeva, In E3S Web of Conferences, 244, 02047 (2021)
9. R. Kulmatov, A. Taylakov, S. Khasanov, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, 28(10), 12245-12255 (2021)
10. Y. Peng, F. Li, N. Xu, R. Kulmatov, K. Gao, G. Wang, Y. Zhang, Y. Qiao, Y. Li, H. Yang, S. Hao, Q. Li, S. Khasanov, Chinese Journal of Eco-Agriculture, 29(2), 312-324 (2021)
11. T. Wehner, R. Naegele, J. Myers, P. Narinder, K. Crosby, Cucurbits, 32 (2020)
12. A. Jumanov, S. Khasanov, A. Tabayev, G. Goziev, U. Uzbekov, E. Malikov, In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, 614(1), 012150 (2020)
13. I. Aslanov, S. Khasanov, Y. Khudaybergenov, M. Groll, Ch. Opp, F. Li, E. Ramirez Del-Valle, In E3S Web of Conferences, 227, 02005 (2021)
E3S Web of Conferences 258, 04024 (2021)
UESF-2021 <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202125804024>

